

SOME PRINCIPLES TO TEACH ENGLISH AT PRIMARY SCHOOL

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Abstract. The teaching-learning is brought about through teaching, the teaching process is the arrangement of the environment within which the students can interact and study how to learn. The process of teaching-learning aims at the transmission of knowledge, imparting skills and formation of attitudes, values and behavior. This article describes some principles to teach English at primary school.

Key words: Young learners, primary education, mistakes, using praise, break, activity.

Teaching primary learners is considered as one of the difficult and interesting process. While writing out verb conjugation tables twenty times over is an effective strategy for adults to learn, you'll be hard-pressed to get first graders to sit still long enough to do the same. If you want to be successful in your teaching at primary school, you need to enjoy teaching primary-aged language learners. You need to be aware at this age that primary young learners are still learning how to hold pens, scissors or even they learning their first foreign language. Sometimes it can be nervous process but you need to be vary patient. Initially, I thought that primary learners should learn English with a bit of drawing, some games and vocabulary. But then I speculate and prefer to teach primary learners focus on themes or topics every lesson. However, teacher should choose topics and themes which learners would interest. For example, fruits, toys or parts of body. The benefits of focusing on topics would help engage learners and remember new words effectively. One of the most important thing to teach young learners is to encourage and reward them during lessons. Rewarding primary learners can be useful thing to help motivating learners to complete the tasks or activities. A stock of stickers of smile faces or stars are can be rewarding for young learners. Moreover, teachers can encourage theirs

learners with positively sentences. In addition, during lessons teacher should give their learners regularly short break due to their limited patience. It is considering significant and necessary tool. Short breaks would be beneficial after complicating one task. Primary learners to have a break from their study: watching a cartoon, sing songs (songs which physical exercises), play some sport outside classroom or play with some toys. Actually, one benefit of break to teachers, in this time teacher can prepare the classroom for the next activity. For example, when the children were watching a cartoon, teacher would take that opportunity to prepare the classroom for painting. Moreover, creative tasks such as painting and drawing which is exiting process for children provide quality of the lesson. Furthermore, Children can create their own picture books in English it is a fun activity too. So is creating cards with pictures in English, using interactive English books and other fun art activities all in English. In young learners teachers should pay attention about their engagement and fun during the lesson. Because they are a key to set a strong foundation for their future education. Here some effective ways to use teaching methods to teach effectively:

Turn lessons into songs. Every English learner, both native and not, is familiar with, at the very least, one classic jingle. Yes, the ABCs are what we turn to for a reminder of what letter comes after Q. Although the middle part (something about *eliemenopee*?) requires a bit more brain power, the song offers English speakers a comfortable reference point for all their alphabetical needs.

Create visual diagrams to illustrate new vocabulary. Head, shoulders, knees, and toes. These are a whole lot easier to point out on a smiling stick man than to write out in a vocabulary list. Visual devices provide a double whammy, too. Students can enjoy coloring or even adding on to pictures, while also absorbing what the new words they are learning *look like*. Highlighting, underlining, and circling are all common visual tricks adults use to recall snippets of information. Creating visual diagrams is the same basic idea, so that the little ones can start to visualize what English looks like. As a bonus, students can more easily locate learning aids

with distinct colors and illustrations among their folders of messy papers.

Break up solitary study sessions with games. Childhood education without games is like chicken wings without seasoning or sauce. You simply can't have one without the other. Games are especially effective teaching methods for young learners, because kids are able to learn without realizing it. Active games let them expel some bottled up energy and quiet ones challenge and require concentration.

Repeat previous lessons in every class. Assuming the average class duration is only an hour or less, that leaves a whole lot of time in the day to forget everything a student just learned. Children won't retain as much information as adults, so repetition is key in English for young learners. Teaching primary learners in English is an engrossing action. As I said above if you love and enjoy teaching young learners, you would be successful in your profession and your children can study their first foreign language which is English efficiently.

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